

the effect of recommended rates of commonly used rice herbicides (see table) on azolla. The study was in a randomized complete block design with four replications.

Azolla caroliniana Willd. was inoculated at 500 g fresh weight/m² immediately after transplanting. Except for oxadiazon applied 3 d before transplanting, all herbicides were applied 4 d after transplanting.

Except for thiobencarb, piperophos - 2, 4-D, and oxadiazon, all herbicides significantly reduced azolla fresh weight by 10 d after treatment. The proprietary mixture of molinate - simetryn - MCPB was most damaging to azolla.

Herbicides did not affect azolla N content.

By 20 d after treatment, all herbicides reduced azolla growth. Molinate - simetryn - MCPB killed all azolla. Thiobencarb was least harmful, reducing

Fresh weight and N content of azolla as affected by herbicide application. ^a IRRI, 1984 wet season.

Treatment	Herbicide rate (kg/ha)	Fresh weight (g/m ²)		N content (%)	
		10 d	20 d	10 d	20 d
Molinate - simetryn - MCPB	0.93	185 f	0 g	2.5 a	—
Butachlor - 2,4-D	1.25	223 ef	32 fg	2.8 a	1.5 a
Butachlor	1.0	310 cdef	77 ef	2.9 a	1.5 a
2,4-D	0.8	216 def	148 ef	2.9 a	2.7 a
Oxyfluorfen	0.14	310 cdef	238 def	2.8 a	2.5 a
Naproanilide - thiobencarb	1.7	348 bcdef	198 defg	2.7 a	2.5 a
Pendimethalin	0.75	383 bcdef	160 efg	2.6 a	2.3 a
Thiobencarb - 2,4-D	1.2	365 bcdef	289 cde	2.6 a	2.4 a
Piperophos - 2,4-D	1.0	485 abcd	191 defg	2.7 a	1.3 a
Oxadiazon	0.75	438 abcde	489 bc	2.5 a	2.6 a
Thiobencarb	1.0	612 a	521 b	2.8 a	2.4 a
Untreated	—	603 a	135 a	2.8 a	2.5 a

^a Observations were made 10 and 20 d after herbicide application. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

azolla fresh weight 29% compared to the untreated check.

The herbicides had no significant effect on azolla N content. However, had azolla been incorporated 20 d after herbicide application, there would have

been significant differences in the amount of N incorporated because of the different fresh weights.

Weed control measures other than herbicides should be used when azolla is grown. *ℒ*

Effect of soil amendments on summer growth and survival of *Azolla pinnata*

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It is difficult to maintain azolla under field conditions in summer in tropical rice growing areas. We studied the effect of soil amendments on summer azolla growth in Apr 1984.

The experiment was in a randomized block design with 4 replications in 1-m² plots. The following amendments were added to the plots and mixed thoroughly: 50 kg P/ha, 50 kg K, 500 kg neem cake, 50 kg diammonium phosphate, 10 t rice husk, 5 t fresh cow dung, 10 t rice husk, 10 t rice chaff, 5 t farmyard manure, and 10 t sawdust, *Azolla pinnata* was inoculated at 400 g/m² in 10-cm-deep water. Fronds floated on the water for 2 d and then settled on the soil. Soil was kept saturated for 3 wk.

The number of fronds, biomass/10 cm², single frond weight, and root length were recorded. Biomass increased

Effect of soil amendments on azolla growth and survival of azolla in summer, Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment	Azolla fronds (no./10 cm ²)	Root length (cm)	Single-frond wt (mg)	Biomass (g/10 cm ²)
Control	96	1.4	47.7	14.3
Superphosphate	114	1.2	49.3	15.3
Muriate of potash	107	1.7	49.7	13.0
Neem cake	193	1.8	52.0	20.3
Diammonium phosphate	222	1.9	62.3	23.7
Farmyard manure	88	1.5	45.7	15.3
Cow dung	223	1.3	61.3	22.0
Rice husk	115	2.4	64.3	21.7
Rice chaff	311	1.8	76.3	35.0
Sawdust	99	2.1	44.0	12.7
SE :	4	0.1	2.0	0.6
SEd :	5	0.2	2.8	0.8

over the control in all treatments except that of K and sawdust. The most fronds survived on rice chaff, which gave the highest single frond weight, followed by cow dung and diammonium phosphate. Rice husk gave the longest root length (see table).

Results showed that soil amendments influence azolla growth and survival in summer. Rice chaff increases moisture holding capacity. Allowing azolla to root may enhance survival over maintaining the fronds in floodwater. *ℒ*

Some physiological studies on rice grown on manganese-deficient soil

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Wheat grown in rotation with rice on coarse Punjab soils is showing increasing Mn deficiency, but rice has shown no visual symptoms. To understand this tolerance mechanism, we grew PR103 in a Mn-deficient (DTPA Mn 0.8 mg/kg) loamy sand soil

Table 1. POE and peroxidase activity in chloroplasts (X) and cytoplasm (Y) in rice leaves, 42 d after transplanting, Ludhiana, India.^a

Mn applied (mg/kg)	POE		Peroxidase	
	A	B	X	Y
0	9	18	0.60	4.8
2.5	14	28	0.48	4.8
5.0	14	28	0.40	5.4
10.0	15	29	0.38	6.4
15.0	16	30	0.39	4.7
20.0	17	32	0.35	4.2

^aA = OD at 620 nm/unit chlorophyll per 5 min; B = OD at 620 nm/100 mg fresh wt per 5 min; X = OD at 660 nm/60 s per unit enzyme in chloroplast; Y = OD at 660 nm/60 s per 100 mg fresh wt in cytoplasm.

in a pot experiment. Four seedlings were transplanted per pot and Mn was applied at 0, 2.5, 5.0, 10.0, 15.0, and 20.0 mg/kg of soil. Chloroplasts were isolated from leaves 21 and 42 d after transplanting and colorimetrically assayed for photosynthetic oxygen evolution (POE). Peroxidase activity in chloroplasts and cytoplasm was determined colorimetrically using guaiacol as substrate. Results at two growth stages were similar. Data for the 42d stage are given here.

Table 2. Elemental composition in rice leaves, yield, and DTPA Mn in soil, Ludhiana, India.

Mn applied (mg/kg)	Composition (mg/kg)				Yield (g/pot)		DTPA Mn in soil (mg/kg)
	Mn	Fe	Fe ²⁺	Zn	Grain	Straw	
0	53	510	174	30	2.4	40	7.7
2.5	71	485	95	32	4.4	42	10.5
5.0	70	402	100	36	5.9	38	11.8
10.0	115	305	104	34	7.2	39	13.4
15.0	81	278	86	36	7.6	39	15.3
20.0	93	265	83	30	8.4	41	19.3

POE was very low in Mn-deficient plants but increased with application of 2.5 mg Mn/kg. Applying more Mn did not proportionately increase POE (Table 1). Chloroplast peroxidase was highest in plants that received no Mn. Cytoplasmic peroxidase increased up to 10 mg Mn/kg and decreased slightly at higher rates.

Elemental analysis of leaves showed Mn concentration increased with Mn supply (Table 2). Fe²⁺ and total Fe content in leaves was highest in 0 Mn plants, indicating an inverse relationship with Mn concentration. Zn concentration did not change with Mn

application.

Grain yield was significantly higher (about 4 times more with 20 mg Mn/kg than with 0 Mn) with Mn application, but straw yield was about the same. Grain filling was incomplete in Mn-deficient plants. DTPA Mn content 42 d after transplanting had increased manyfold in all pots due to reduction under submerged conditions.

Results indicate that although rice plants did not show symptoms of Mn deficiency, low Mn decreased photosynthetic activity and impaired translocation of photosynthates to grain. *ℓ*

The Na-K ratio as index of salt stress in rice cultures

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We screened 16 rices for salt tolerance in coastal soils in South Gujarat.

Grain yield, and K and Na content, and their ratios in different rices, Navsari, India.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)	K (%)	Na (%)	Na:K
IET7587	2.6	0.51	1.05	2.06
IET7589	2.9	0.45	1.16	2.58
IET7908	1.8	0.36	1.05	2.92
IET7910	2.5	0.36	0.91	2.53
IET7911	2.3	0.32	0.91	2.84
IET6993	2.1	0.39	1.10	2.82
IET6996	2.6	0.40	1.17	2.92
IET7337	2.8	0.38	1.06	2.79
IET7588	3.4	0.52	0.99	1.90
IET7912	2.1	0.38	0.87	2.29
IR2031-729-2	3.5	0.57	0.68	1.19
SLR51214	2.8	0.40	1.04	2.60
CD at 5%	1.1	0.10	0.20	

SLR51214 was the check variety. At transplanting, soil had ECe 9.0 dS/m, pH 8.6, and ESP 25.

Twelve entries performed uniformly and at par with SLR51214. Grains were analyzed for nutrient content and Na:K was calculated (see table). K content varied from 0.32 to 0.57. IR2031-729-2 had highest K and lowest Na and yielded highest. Na:K for most varieties

was above 2.5. However, IR2031-729-2 had 1.19 and IET7588 had 1.90, indicating a preferential absorption of K over Na.

Yield and K content were highly and positively correlated ($r = 0.96$). The relation between yield and Na content was not significant. Na:K, however, was significantly and negatively correlated with yield ($r = -0.82$). *ℓ*

Azolla as a substitute for N fertilizer in rice cultivation

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In 1980-81 in Bhubaneswar, we studied azolla as a substitute for N fertilizer in rice cultivation. Soil was a laterite with pH 5.6, CEC 3.5 meq/100 g soil, 0.36% C, 0.35% N, 0.45% P, 1.55% K, 70.1%

sand, 16.3% silt, and 12% clay. The experiment was in a randomized block design with three replications. All plots received 10 cartloads of farmyard manure, 13.3 kg P, and 24.9 kg K/ha before transplanting Pusa 2-21 (IR8/TKM6). Azolla was surface applied or multiplied in situ 1 wk before transplanting. Plots received azolla alone or azolla with urea fertilizer (see table).

All treatments yielded more than the control. Applying 10 t azolla/ha